

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

Deliverable 2.5: General Questionnaire to Be Used from Stakeholders After the End of the Project

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Executive Summary

This report presents a questionnaire tool developed within the AGEMERA project, targeting stakeholders in mineral exploration and mining. The primary objective is to create a reusable questionnaire for assessing public perceptions and social sustainability related to the exploration and mining of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) across diverse cultural and geographic contexts. In addition to the AGEMERA project's focus on innovative technologies in the CRM sector, it also aims to empower communities by providing stakeholders with this questionnaire beyond the project's duration.

The questionnaire contains questions for insights into local community perceptions of mining and exploration activities, capturing attitudes at a specific time and within a defined regional context. However, the data gathered using the questionnaire represent solely the perspectives of individuals who would be successfully approached through survey distribution and chose to participate. The results of such public surveys typically reflect a self-selected segment of the population, influenced by factors such as interest levels, accessibility to the questionnaire, and local awareness.

The questionnaire experienced a pilot phase in Finnish municipalities at the beginning of 2023 and was subsequently adapted for wider implementation in Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia in 2024. Wider deployment necessitated adjustments to local factors such as variations in language, educational systems, occupational frameworks, regional corporate presence, and mapping data. This process emphasized the significance of context in survey design and made the questionnaire flexible to different institutional and cultural settings.

A follow-up survey conducted in 2025 across Finland, Germany, and Estonia yielded additional information, illustrating the potential evolution of public perceptions over time. The capacity to monitor changes significantly increases the questionnaire's practicality in assessing the social license to operate, which refers to the ongoing (in-)acceptance and (dis-)approval that an organization or industry receives from its stakeholders and the public for its activities.

Although the questionnaire is widely applicable, challenges emerged during its implementation. Political sensitivities and insufficient municipal cooperation in certain regions can impede outreach efforts. Survey participation can vary due to digital infrastructure constraints, social trust levels, and interest in exploration and mining-related issues. Contextual barriers should be considered when interpreting results and planning future deployments for the questionnaire.

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List of Acronyms

AB	Advisory Board
BuildERS	Building European Communities Resilience and Social Capital project
CRM	Critical Raw Material
CRMA	Critical Raw Materials Act
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LGOM	Legnica-Głogów Copper District
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
REA	Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

One of the AGEMERA project's focuses is developing a general-purpose questionnaire for stakeholders who are either affected by or directly involved in the exploration and mining of critical raw materials. The questionnaire evaluates public perceptions, improves community engagement, and facilitates sustainability assessments in exploration and mining contexts. During the project's initial six months, the questionnaire was developed in English in January 2023 [1] and translated to Finnish language to pilot in Finland in February 2023.

The questionnaire is organized around interconnected themes to gather public perceptions, experiences, and attitudes regarding mineral exploration and mining activities. The questionnaire primarily gathers demographic and socioeconomic data from respondents, including age, education level, employment status, and regional affiliation. A central theme is the extent to which respondents are aware of and have first-hand experience with mineral exploration. The theme pertains to the perceived advantages and disadvantages of mining, encompassing both economic and social dimensions. Participants are requested to consider the distribution of benefits and evaluate whether specific groups (e.g., residents, businesses, governments) receive disproportionate advantages.

The questionnaire examines regional economic perspectives by asking participants to identify sectors deemed crucial for their region's future and to articulate their hopes and concerns about economic transformation. It also examines the perceived capacity of individuals and communities to impact decisions regarding exploration and mining. It includes trust in corporations, governmental institutions, and participatory mechanisms, while assessing public perceptions regarding their respect and inclusion in decision-making processes.

Environmental attitudes constitute a fundamental component of the questionnaire. Respondents are additionally asked regarding their trust in institutions and information sources, including government authorities, mining companies, scientists, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and media outlets, to assess perceptions of credibility and transparency among various stakeholders. Moreover, the questionnaire examines the theme of place attachment and regional identity, exploring why individuals select or maintain connections to specific regions and how such identities influence their perspectives on mining and development. For this reason, it includes a spatial component via map-based questions. Participants are invited to identify regions they consider appropriate or inappropriate for extractive activities, providing insights into public perceptions of the local landscape and the acceptability of mineral exploration and mining in designated areas. An open comment section allows respondents to voice additional concerns, suggestions, or issues not covered by the structured questions, enhancing the questionnaire's inclusivity and responsiveness.

The questionnaire was utilized during the pilot phase conducted in February 2023 in the Finnish municipalities of Kuusamo, Posio, and Rovaniemi. This phase evaluated the clarity, content, and contextual appropriateness of the questionnaire. Adjustments were made to enhance applicability based on findings evaluated in July 2023. The revised version was implemented from March to May 2024 in Germany, Estonia, Poland, and Zambia. The process entailed translation to respective languages, modifying the questionnaire to capture the distinct characteristics of each region, encompassing differences in educational systems, occupational classifications, local company presence, and pertinent geographic data for map-based elements. This contextual adaptation conforms to recognized best practices in cross-cultural survey design, ensuring the tool's relevance and effectiveness in various settings. A follow-up survey was conducted in April 2025 across Finland, Germany, and Poland to assess the effectiveness of the questionnaire for longitudinal monitoring.

The questionnaire was deployed in different regions to check its adaptability across various institutional, linguistic, and socio-cultural contexts. The project team acknowledged the significance of cultural and contextual sensitivity in survey research and conducted a comprehensive localisation process for each of the five case study regions: Finland, Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia.

1.2 Objective of the Report

- To present a general questionnaire for mineral exploration and mining sector stakeholders. It can be an adaptable tool for community engagement, public perception assessment, and sustainability evaluations in CRM mining and exploration-related contexts, extending its utility beyond the duration of the AGEMERA project.
- To emphasise the questionnaire's practical application while concisely detailing its creation, including localisation and deployment, throughout five culturally separate regions. This historical context aims to help stakeholders understand the questionnaire's adaptability to various regional contexts.
- To provide an outline to prospective stakeholders that can be utilised or tailored to meet specific requirements and local contexts when using the general questionnaire tool.

2 General Stakeholder Survey for Evaluating Local Perspectives on Mineral Exploration

In this chapter, the general questionnaire, a slightly modified version of Deliverable 2.1 from the AGEMERA project, "Questionnaire about Social Sustainability and Acceptance of Mineral Exploration and Mining" [1], is presented. The original draft, submitted as a formal project deliverable, can be found online at https://agemera.eu/assets/content/publications/AGEMERA_D2.1.pdf.

A few modifications were made to enhance the questionnaire's readability, applicability, and flexibility in different local contexts, as outlined in Deliverable 2.1. New response options were added to the socioeconomic status and employment sections to represent a wider variety of professions and industry roles that align with regional economic structures. The questionnaire's "Relationship with the home region" theme was introduced immediately after the socioeconomic section to better capture regional ties at the outset of the survey. In addition, respondents are now asked which municipality they are referring to, acknowledging that some may not live in the area but still have strong connections to it. A new question was added to the "Mineral exploration in the home region" theme to determine whether respondents had directly contacted mining or mineral exploration companies or had been approached by them. New statements were added to the section on environmental damages and concerns, including opinions on mining in areas designated for nature conservation and a willingness to pay more for minerals sourced sustainably.

2.1 Age, gender, and education

2.1.1 Year of birth

2.1.2 Are you ...

- a) Female
- b) Male
- c) Other
- d) Rather not say

2.1.3 What is your level of education? Choose the highest level of education you have.

- a) Still in a comprehensive school
- b) Primary education
- c) Upper-secondary education
- d) Specialized vocational training or college-level training

e) Higher education

f) Other

2.2 Socioeconomic status and employment sector

2.2.1 Which of the following options best describes your current situation?

a) Employed

b) Unemployed

c) Student

d) Retired

e) Stay-at-home mother or father, family carer

f) In military or non-military national service

g) A leading position in the service of another

h) Worker

i) Entrepreneur or self-employed

j) Other

2.2.2 Choose the sector you currently work in or last worked in

a) Public administration or national defence

b) Education and training

c) Health care and social services

d) Tourism

e) Construction

f) Logistics

g) Energy

h) Wellness

i) Creative

j) Extractive

k) Industry and manufacturing

l) Commerce

- m) Natural resources
- n) Other
- o) I don't have an occupational history.

2.3 Relationship with the home region

- 2.3.1 Your primary municipality of residence is
- 2.3.2 What is your home postal code?
- 2.3.3 What is your relationship with the area? For example, are you from that area, do you work there, or do you own land or a cottage in the region?
- 2.3.4 How many years have you lived in the region?
- 2.3.5 How long do you think you will be living in the region?
 - a) Fewer than 5 years
 - b) 5–10 years
 - c) 10–20 years
 - d) Over 20 years
 - e) I don't know
- 2.3.6 What matters have affected or are affecting your choice to live in your current home region?
- 2.3.7 If you are planning to move, what would make you change your mind and stay in the area where you currently live?
- 2.3.8 Which municipality does your answer concern?

2.4 Mineral exploration in the home region

- 2.4.1 Are you aware of the mineral exploration occurring in your home region?
- 2.4.2 Have you ever been in contact with the following mineral exploration or mining company, or have any companies contacted you?
- 2.4.3 Did you initiate contact with the mineral exploration or mining companies, or have they contacted you?
- 2.4.4 If you wish, you may say more about your experiences with mineral exploration companies

2.5 Views on mineral exploration and mining

2.5.1 To what extent do you accept mineral exploration and mining?

Completely disagree, somewhat disagree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat agree, completely agree, I don't know

- a) I generally approve of mineral exploration.
- b) I approve of mineral exploration in my home region.
- c) I generally approve of mining.
- d) I approve of mining in my home region.

2.5.2 I hope that exploration leads to the opening of a mine in my home region

Nine-point Likert scale; completely disagree ... completely agree

2.5.3 How does mineral exploration affect your home region?

2.5.4 How does mineral exploration affect you and your family?

2.6 Distribution of harms and benefits

2.6.1 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

- a) Mineral exploration benefits the local economy.
- b) Mineral exploration benefits villages and people living near the exploration sites.
- c) Mineral exploration benefits me personally.
- d) The costs and benefits of mineral exploration are evenly distributed in my home municipality.
- e) Mineral exploration positively affects the operating environment of their businesses.
- f) Mineral exploration has a negative effect on investments made by other businesses in the region.
- g) Mineral exploration does more harm than good to my home region.
- h) Mineral exploration primarily benefits people other than those of my home region.
- i) Large-scale mining projects are necessary to the vitality of my home region.
- j) Large-scale mining projects are a threat to small-scale local entrepreneurship.

2.6.2 How concerned are you about the effects mineral exploration has on other businesses in your home region?

Nine-point Likert scale; not at all concerned ... very concerned

2.7 Economy and the future

2.7.1 How do you see the future of your home region? Choose three economic sectors that in your opinion are the most important for the vitality of the area.

- a) Education and research
- b) Health care and social services
- c) National defense
- d) Tourism
- e) Construction
- f) Logistics
- g) Energy
- h) Wellness
- i) Creative
- j) Extractive
- k) Industry and manufacturing
- l) Commerce
- m) Natural resources
- n) Other

2.7.2 Continuing to think about the future of your home region, choose three economic sectors that in your opinion are the least important for the vitality of the area.

- a) Education and research
- b) Health care and social services
- c) National defense
- d) Tourism
- e) Construction
- f) Logistics

- g) Energy
- h) Wellness
- i) Creative
- j) Extractive
- k) Industry and manufacturing
- l) Commerce
- m) Natural resources
- n) Other

2.7.3 If you wish, you may elaborate and say more about your views concerning your home region's future economy.

2.8 Threats and opportunities

2.8.1 When you think about the year 2050, what do you consider the biggest threats to your home region?

2.8.2 What is best that can happen to your home region by 2050?

2.9 Impacts on the local community

2.9.1 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements concerning mineral exploration's social impacts?

Completely disagree, somewhat disagree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat agree, completely agree, I don't know

- a) Mineral exploration has a positive effect on the local atmosphere.
- b) Mineral exploration can be openly discussed in the locality.
- c) Mineral exploration divides opinions and thus negatively affects the community spirit in the locality.
- d) Mineral exploration causes uncertainty about the future of the region.
- e) Mineral exploration improves the opportunities of future generations to live in the area.

2.9.2 How concerned are you about the effect mineral exploration has on the community spirit in your home region?

Nine-point Likert scale; not at all concerned ... very concerned

2.10 Participation and influence

2.10.1 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements concerning local people's participation and influence?

Completely disagree, somewhat disagree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat agree, completely agree, I don't know

- a) Local people's opinions don't have much of an effect on the decision-making concerning the extractive sector.
- b) Mineral exploration companies are open and transparent about their operations.
- c) Mineral exploration companies don't listen to local people's concerns and wishes.
- d) Mineral exploration companies respect local people.
- e) Authorities take local people's concerns seriously.
- f) Legislation guarantees local people sufficient opportunities to influence matters concerning mining.

2.10.2 Who do you think should be compensated for the harm caused by mineral exploration? What should that compensation be like?

2.11 Environmental damage and environmental concerns

2.11.1 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Completely disagree, somewhat disagree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat agree, completely agree, I don't know

- a) Science and technology will solve environmental problems without people having to change their lifestyle much.
- b) The severity of environmental problems is often exaggerated.
- c) I am often confused about what is good and what is bad for the environment.
- d) Human activities should be adjusted to nature's carrying capacity.
- e) Nature is resilient and thus able to recover even from heavy stress caused by human activities.
- f) It is necessary to open new mines to combat climate change.
- g) Material consumption should be restricted by political means.

h) I am willing to pay more for products that are made using responsibly produced minerals.

i) The EU should strive to be as self-sufficient as possible when it comes to the production of minerals.

j) Activities of the mining sector in nature conservation areas are acceptable

2.11.2 How concerned are you about environmental matters generally?

Nine-point Likert scale; not at all concerned ... very concerned

2.11.3 How concerned are you about mineral exploration's effects on the environment in your home region?

Nine-point Likert scale; not at all concerned ... very concerned

2.11.4 To what extent do the environmental problems associated with mining affect your views on mineral exploration?

Nine-point Likert scale; not at all ... very much

2.12 Trust in different actors

2.12.1 When it comes to matters concerning the extractive sector, how much do you trust the following?

Very much, relatively much, neither much nor little, relatively little, very little, I don't know

a) European Union

b) National political decision-making

c) Local political decision-making

d) Supervisory authorities

e) Scientific community

f) Environmental organizations

g) Reindeer Herders' Association

h) Mineral exploration companies

i) Mining companies

j) Traditional media

k) Social media

l) Close friends/relatives

2.13 Where do you get reliable information about extractive sector projects in your home region?

2.14 Map-based items

Mineral potential areas have been pre-marked on the map. Areas with critical raw material potential are marked in yellow and those with other mineral potential are marked in turquoise. Critical raw materials are materials that are strategically and economically important but whose supply is associated with high risk.

2.14.1 Mark the areas that in your opinion are suitable for extractive sector use.

2.14.2 Mark the areas that in your opinion should be left untouched.

2.14.3 To what extent did the location of critical minerals affect the areas you marked on the map?

Nine-point Likert scale; not at all ... very much

2.15 Feedback and other matters

2.15.1 How did you find the survey?

- a) Through a local newspaper
- b) Through social media
- c) Through a friend/relative

If you wish, you may comment on the survey or mention a matter that was not raised in the survey.

3 Implementation of the Questionnaire in Diverse Local Contexts

3.1 Historical Background and Context

Using the questionnaire, AGEMERA public survey was conducted across five cultural perspectives and geographically distinct case study regions: northeast Estonia, northern Finland, Germany's Erzgebirge region, Poland's Lower Silesia, and Zambia's North-Western Province. These areas are characterised by distinct past events, economic circumstances, ecological landscapes, and phases of exploration and mining-related development.

Surveys of this nature provide a temporal and spatial snapshot of local perceptions regarding the exploration and mining of raw materials. The results represent the perspectives of individuals who were a) reachable via advertising platforms and b) inclined or motivated to engage in the survey. The findings do not represent whole populations; instead, they offer a focused perspective within the region's participant group.

The execution phase of the survey identified various practical and context-dependent challenges. Political tensions and local scepticism regarding mining activities impeded comprehensive cooperation in certain regions. Some municipalities opted not to participate in or endorse the distribution of the survey, which may affect response rates and the diversity of participants. These constraints should be taken into account when analysing the data.

3.2 Record of Implementation in Countries

3.2.1 Estonia [2]

The survey was conducted in the northeastern region of Estonia, explicitly targeting the vicinity of Rakvere. This region comprises ten municipalities and has a population of approximately 65,000 residents. It is historically rich and culturally significant, characterized by valuable farmland and evidence of ancient habitation dating back to 8700 BC. Plans for phosphorite mining during the Soviet era in the 1970s and 1980s prompted considerable public environmental activism and political involvement. These events laid the groundwork for a lasting awareness of ecological and mining concerns. European mineral policy renewed interest in local phosphorite and graptolite argillite resources, prompting the Estonian Geological Service to resume its surveys. The region encompasses operational construction material quarries and is near the established oil shale industry of Ida-Viru County.

3.2.2 Finland [2]

The Finnish case study included the municipalities of Kuusamo, Posio, Rovaniemi. Rovaniemi serves as an expanding administrative and commercial centre in Lapland. Kuusamo, situated on the Russian border, is a sparsely populated municipality characterized by a population decline and a robust tourism sector. The municipalities are witnessing heightened interest from international mining companies due to the EU Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA), which facilitates licensing procedures for strategically important projects. This interest aligns with the expansion of tourism and renewable energy efforts. Implementing the survey in Finland leveraged established regional governance networks and public infrastructure; however, local tensions related to land use and tourism were also observed.

3.2.3 Germany [2]

The questionnaire survey utilized Germany's Erzgebirge region in the Free State of Saxony as a case study site. This region, referred to in English as the Ore Mountains, represents Europe's most densely populated low mountain range and has a continuous mining history spanning over 800 years. The Erzgebirge, designated as a UNESCO World Heritage Site, encompasses a diverse collection of historic mining towns, advancements in water management, and smelting locations. The region's extensive mining heritage shapes its identity and local economy. The implementation of the survey in Saxony was influenced by the region's cultural pride in its mining heritage, while also facing challenges related to shifting views on environmental conservation versus resource development.

3.2.4 Poland [2]

The questionnaire was implemented in the Lower Silesia region of Poland, with a specific emphasis on the Legnica-Głogów Copper District (LGOM). The area, situated near Legnica and Lubin, is historically significant due to its mining industry, which has been operational since the 1960s. It is readily accessible through major highways, railways, and an international airport in Wrocław. The Polish case exhibits industrial identity, highlighted by KGHM Polska Miedź, a leading global copper producer. Historical mining sites, such as Złoty Stok and the Wałbrzych Science and Art Centre, contribute significantly to the region's cultural depth. The established mining culture facilitated the implementation of surveys, despite concerns regarding environmental impacts and urban expansion.

3.2.5 Zambia [2]

The case study area in Zambia was the North-Western Province, with a population exceeding 1.27 million and a density of approximately twenty people per square kilometer. Mining is the province's primary economic activity, featuring significant copper mines in Solwezi, including Kansanshi, Lumwana, and Kalumbila. This rural area has undergone notable demographic and social transformations due to an influx of

workers from various regions. Communities such as Manyama have emerged due to mining development. The survey encountered logistical difficulties due to low population density and varying degrees of digital access.

4 Recommendations for Adapting and Implementing the Questionnaire Beyond AGEMERA

Given the importance of understanding local public perceptions in mining and exploration projects, a standardised questionnaire can serve as a valuable tool for collecting structured data and supporting informed decision-making. Specifically, the questionnaire can assist with the following tasks:

- establishing a baseline understanding of community opinions before the start of exploration or mining activities;
- monitoring shifts in public attitudes throughout the project lifecycle by conducting one or more follow-up surveys;
- evaluating the effectiveness of engagement, communication, and mitigation strategies; fostering open dialogue and strengthening community trust.

Based on experiences gained from piloting the questionnaire in Finland, Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia, it is recommended that local conditions shall be carefully considered when applying the AGEMERA questionnaire in different countries. This involves not only translating the language but also making contextual adaptations, which may include:

- the use of appropriate terminology, based on the local situation (e.g., education system, job titles, institutions);
- the integration of map-based elements relevant to the region;
- the use of local examples to replace industry terms and corporate names.

As previously mentioned, the questionnaire may be used to conduct continuous studies. Follow-up surveys in Finland, Germany, and Poland in April 2025 demonstrate the questionnaire's ability to track changes over time and capture changing sentiments. This allows for observing how the social license evolves over time in a local context.

To ensure that the questionnaire is implemented successfully in future situations, the following suggestions are made:

- Identify key stakeholder groups, such as local communities near exploration and or mining sites, policymakers and regulators, industry professionals and geologists, NGOs and environmental organizations.
- Adapt the questionnaire as needed, while ensuring that the questions remain neutral and accessible. Use plain language for non-expert audiences and avoid technical jargon unless the questionnaire is specifically aimed at experts.

- Test the revised questionnaire with a small, diverse sample and make adjustments based on the feedback received.
- Distribute the questionnaire through multiple channels to maximize accessibility. This may include online platforms, paper-based formats, and in-person collection.
- Ensure full general data protection regulation (GDPR) compliance by clearly informing participants how their data will be collected, used, and stored.
- Be mindful that the distribution method and promotional strategy can influence who responds. This may introduce sampling bias, so it is essential to analyze and clean the collected data properly.
- To enhance understanding and context, consider combining the survey data with other relevant qualitative sources (e.g., interviews, focus groups, or case studies) during the evaluation procedure.

5 Conclusion

This report describes a general-purpose questionnaire developed during the AGEMERA project to assess public opinion regarding mineral exploration and mining. The questionnaire, designed for long-term stakeholder engagement, has been tested in five culturally diverse regions through pilot surveys and subsequent surveys conducted during the project.

The questionnaire provides localized, time-bound viewpoints from participants who are reachable and eager to participate in the survey. Although it offers insightful information, its findings should be interpreted in light of participant reach and motivational constraints.

Adjustments to the local situation of case study sites provided effectiveness and contextual relevance. Notwithstanding obstacles, such as a lack of internet access and municipal cooperation, the questionnaire demonstrated flexibility in various contexts.

The general questionnaire, an outcome of the AGEMERA project, is a valuable and adaptable resource for stakeholders dedicated to developing transparent, inclusive, and socially responsible CRM projects.

6 References

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